

**IN THE PROCESS OF LEARNING THE ENGLISH LANGUAGE, MOST FACE THE
PROBLEMS THAT COME**

**Against state of the university pedagogical institute of foreign
language and literature in the direction of 1- phase,
106-group of students
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Annotatsiya: This article in the English language to learn who begin students between face that come some of the problems are and to them issued ba'zi recommendations the need will take.

Key words: problem, recommended , the English language, new words mind to take , speech.

Annotasiya: v a mi ostanovimsya nekotorig problemax its state is neither, s kotorimi stalkivayutsya the student, kotorie tolko nachinayut izuchat angliyskiy yazik, a takje nekotorig sovetax nixol neither beginning.

Klyuchevie slovo: problema, rekomendasiya, angliyskiy yazik, zapominanie novix slovar re after.

Annotation: in this article, we will focus on the problem of some students who are just starti by the face, its to learn English, as well as some tips I have for.

Keywords: problem, recommendation, English, memorization of new words, speech.

In today's rapidly changing with developing and growing zamonimizda qualified and foreign language better who knows specialist personnel demand increased has. This regard from, foreign languages , in particular, English is the language to learn , and to teach the need and the attention increased has. This is proof of as, even in kindergarten from the age of

starting children a foreign language , in particular English language teaching that go to show you can. You know, the English language in the world, eight international languages one is, today's day is not only for the local population and representatives of colloquial language it is, and finally, inter-country bilateral relations ,diplomatic and other relations get in the go an important role earned continues. So it's, this language, the requirements increased to have a go as, new methods , new language tutorial for innovation work out of, this in spite of, the English language learning process in the students some of the problems that face will come.

Literature review and methodology

For example, language study , new words mind to the right that it is natural. Thus, basically , new words, memorize the reader it is certain a time after quickly forget sends. For this reason, the word mind taking after it repeat not stand , and practice in applied. The word mind getting again a recommended is, new words to face if you come, it's yourself better seen in the place to write or attached to put. Thus, the words any of you see when you can repeat and at least this word in the day 3-4 times your eyes into required are. If this I recommend a months during if used ,the words of 99% in the accuracy of memory engraved will remain. The word in mind another one I recommend , it speech is used. That you for example " to do "behavior study did suppose, it just " to do - make do, make" , in the form of mind get every time is also effective results does not give. It samples and in the speech of the application through to learn more effect it gives. I.e. the same word with the sentence of the conclusion , or a combination in the form of mind get can. Again, a method is, of the word only o'zinigina not, his synonymous of and antonimi with along study. Thus, language, cognitive , one not , but a studying three words learned will be. New word mind before we have too suppose , it is in practice used, he, of course, quickly keep in mind is that out is going to. This problem solution , while repeated is to stand, for example, we rid of the test work through also new in the studied words repeated stand can.

Discuss

School or other educational ourselves in a lesson transported at the time native - language a lot and the unstated use also attention is focused have that the problems of one. This reader or the language learn the English language in speech development ground be can . This solution as that offer is made , I would have, the small of a fine introduction to through this problem to up to solve can, for example , native in the language of one 's work to the reader and the English language in a poem or a song to tell the giving of fine apply can. Thus, language study known as to up the English language to speak learnsif to a fine subject , the fine performance for a new poem or song in mind to take on a come up, this is through the student the word wealth increases, and finally, this with learn "speaking" skills begun the form has.

Their own on not wanting to work or to himself disregarded. This language to teach face who came again a problem . Teachers' assignments on time done or incomplete, complete , serious yondashmaslik also language learning in the process to difficulties lead cause can. This solution as the only lessons in the process the knowledge to get and language learning with limited did not remain , given to the topic relevant additional information to learn , them repeat strengthening to stand recommended are .

Basically, the English language now learning students in front of again a serious problem is, learning in the language of error to speak of being put is afraid. Naturally , every a new starting work, mistakes and shortcomings occurs and this is a normal condition since . This is the reason for not only the English language learning process but also in general science while taking mistakes to make not afraid , the error of the way that put in the case from the conclusions make , re - this bug in the way that does not put the effort to make it should.

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